

Agronomic characteristics

Shallow water		Knee-deep water				Semideep water				Deep water	
Transplanting		Transplanting		Direct sowing/transpl.		Direct sowing/transpl.		Direct sowing		Direct sowing	
Veg. stage	Mat. stage	Veg. stage	Mat. stage	Veg. stage	Mat. stage	Veg. stage	Mat. stage	Veg. stage	Mat. stage	Veg. stage	Mat. stage
Aug.-Sept.	Oct.-Nov.	Jul.-Sept.	Oct.-Nov.	Jul.-Sept.	Oct.-Nov.	June-Sept.	Oct.-Dec.	June-Sept.	Oct.-Dec.	May-Sept.	Oct.-Dec.
10-60cm	45-15cm	20-90cm	60-15cm	20-110cm	90-25cm	20-120cm	110-25cm	30-160cm	120-60cm	More than 160cm	
depth	depth	depth	depth	depth	depth	depth	depth	depth	depth	depth	
2.5-4.5 t/ha		2.5-3.5 t/ha		2.5-3.5 t/ha		2.5-3.0 t/ha		2.5-3.0 t/ha		2.0-3.0 t/ha	

Duration: E = early; M = medium; L = late. Grain quality: m = medium; mc = medium coarse; c = coarse. Kernel color: W = white; R = red.

The extent of adaptation (indicated by arrows) of the rice varieties and their yield potentialities in relation to varying depths and durations of waterlogged situations at vegetative (veg.) and maturing (mat.) stages under direct sown and transplanted conditions. Rice Research Station, Chinsurah, West Bengal, India.

Promising rice varieties for different types of low-lying waterlogged situations

S. K. Datta and B. Banerji, Rice Research Station, Chinsurah, West Bengal, India

Several recommended rice varieties were tested under common water situations – shallow water, knee-deep water, semideep water, and deep water – at the Rice Research Station, Chinsurah, West Bengal, during the monsoon season of 1971 – 72. The varieties were evaluated for suitability to different types of waterlogged areas and to meet farmers’ needs. Eight specially constructed fields were used to study the plants growing at varying depths and varying duration of waterlogged situations. The soil was clay loam with pH of 6.9. No manure was applied.

The accompanying figure names some varieties that show promise for different

low-lying situations, their grain quality and duration characteristics, and their yield potentialities under direct-sown and transplanted conditions. Such information may help rice workers formulate effective recommendations for varietal suitability, choice of grain types, and time of harvest for different low-lying waterlogged situations.

Alternate sources of dwarfism

M. J. Balakrishna Rao, Central Rice Research Institute (CRRI), Cuttack, Orissa, India

Because most of the short-culmed varieties are derived from Dee-geo-woo-gen, scientists at CRRI are investigating possible alternate dwarf gene sources from Japan, China, and Indonesia, and are generating short-culmed lines through mutation. Japonicas are of particular interest among alternate dwarf gene sources.

Scientists at the Central Rice Research institute, Cuttack, India, are using as alternate dwarf gene sources japonica varieties such as Hoyoku an Shiranui (above) and Jikkoku.